

INVESTIGATION OF HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS'
STEREOTYPED THOUGHTS ABOUT FOREIGN LANGUAGE
AND ENGLISH SELF-EFFICACY PERCEPTIONS
IN TERMS OF SOME VARIABLES

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Abstract:

The aim of this study is to examine the relationship between stereotyped thoughts about foreign language and English self-efficacy perception of high school students in terms of various variables. 900 students from different high schools in Ankara, Turkey attended this study as a sample group. Data were collected through "Scale for Stereotyped Thoughts about Foreign Language" (Ünal, 2015) and "English Self-efficacy Perception" (Yanar, 2008). t-Test, one way ANOVA, Kruskal Wallis, Mann Whitney U, Tamhane, LSD, Pearson correlation, Regression analysis was used to analyze the data. This study was designed with comparative correlational survey design. There is statistically significant difference in their stereotyped thoughts about foreign language in terms of private/state high school, the aim of learning English variables. There are statistically significant differences in their foreign language self-efficacy perceptions in terms of private/state high school, weekly studying hours, and the aim of learning English variables. Pearson-r correlation revealed no significant relationship between the Stereotyped Thoughts toward foreign language and English Self-efficacy Perception of Students. Regression analysis showed that stereotyped thoughts can not predict English self-efficacy.

Keywords: stereotyped thoughts, self-efficacy, foreign language, teaching

1. Introduction

Language is defined as the word that people use to express their thoughts and feelings (Turkish Language Society, 2018). If it were not language, there would be no communication. Universal values in the stages of modernization, the advance of foreign

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language are an indisputable reality (İnal, 2016). The realization of such a sharing in our globalizing world depends on learning the language of the developing society and the culture of the advanced, high-tech, in addition to the main languages of the individual (Er, 2007). Experience in failure to learn language in adults can affect motivation in language learning and lead to failures (Schachter, 1989).

Language provides to transfer the thoughts. The thoughts lead and affect the feelings and behaviours. Stereotyped thoughts disorder and obstructions towards people or lessons originated from unrealistic negative thoughts of people (Ünal, 2015). While anyone reflecting the thoughts, it is needed to know the structure of the thought, language expressions and language. So, traditional language theories are also thought theories (Pollock, 1982). The stereotype thoughts are set of negative, unrealistic, and unreasonable thoughts affecting our emotions and behaviours. These behaviours are resistant to change (Dökmen, 2008). The beliefs of the learners are an important factor in learning. The inherent learning chain is: beliefs shape attitudes, influence motivation in human behaviors, eventually expected learning occurs (Öz, 2005). Students must assess the advantages and disadvantages of stereotyped ideas and overcome potential difficulties. It is possible to identify stereotypes and trends of students (Houghton, 2010).

Self-efficacy means People's beliefs about their capabilities to produce designated levels of performance that exercise influence over events that affect their lives. Judgment as to how successful individuals can be to overcome the difficult situations they may face in the future (Bandura, 1971). It is important to increase the self-efficacy perceptions of students on foreign language, to learn foreign language (Bandura, 1993). Most students are having difficulty in learning a second foreign language. In order to overcome these difficulties, it is necessary to identify difficulties experienced by students and to encourage them to learn foreign languages (Kannan, 2009). It is necessary to make studies about how to improve these perceptions by determining students' self-efficacy perception. Self-efficacy perception affects motivation and success feelings of students (Torres, 2001). The stereotyped thoughts toward foreign language and English self-efficacy perception of students were investigated in the study to help students learn foreign language better. The study focuses on the following questions:

1. Is there a significant difference between the stereotyped thoughts about foreign language of high school students and;
 - a) Private high school/ state high school
 - b) Weekly study hours
 - c) English learning aims?
2. Is there a significant difference between English self-efficacy perception of high school students and;
 - a) Private high school/ state high school;
 - b) Weekly study hours;
 - c) English learning aims.

3. Is there a correlation between the stereotyped thoughts about foreign language and English self-efficacy perception of high school students?
4. Can stereotyped thoughts about foreign language of high school students predict English self-efficacy perception of students?

2. Methods

2.1. Research Model

The design of the study was comparative correlational survey model, which is one of the common forms of quantitative researches. Correlational design can be defined as the statistical test used to determine the tendency or pattern for two (or more) variables or sets of data to vary consistently (Creswell, 2012). The students' demographics included private/ state high school, weekly study hours, English learning aims.

2.2. Study Group

The set of participants were 900 students studying in Science High School, Anatolian High School, Social Sciences High School, Anatolian Religious High School, Vocational and Technical Anatolian High School. % 63,3 (569) of participants were women, % 36,8 (331) of the participants were men.

2.3. Data Collection Tool

"The stereotyped thoughts about foreign language scale" developed by Menderes Ünal (2015) consists of 42 items indicating from 1 "disagreement" to 5 "strongly agreement". The scale was used to determine the stereotyped thoughts of the students. Chronbach's alpha coefficient for the scale is ,87. If the Chronbach's alpha coefficient is more than ,70, it is accepted enough for the reliability of general test scores (Büyüköztürk, 2015).

"English Self-efficacy Perceptions Scale" was developed by Burcu Hancı Yanar (2008) consists of 34 items indicating from 1 "disagreement" to 5 "strongly agreement". The scale was used to determine the level English self-efficacy beliefs. Chronbach's alpha coefficient for the scale is ,97.

2.4. Data Analysis

Test of normality was applied to decide the distribution of the data. One way ANOVA, t-test, Kruskal Wallis, Mann Whitney U, Pearson correlation, Regression analysis were used to analyze the data. LSD and Tamhane tests were used as the post hoc tests. Post-hoc tests are used to figure out which group in the sample differs. If the variances are equal, LSD tests can be used. Whereas, variances neither are nor equal, Tamhane can be used. Sampling is not equal for the tests (Kayri, 2009).

3. Results

The findings are presented as below.

1a) "Is there a significant difference between the stereotyped thoughts about foreign language of high school students as to private high school/ state high school?"

Table 1: t-Tests Results of Stereotyped Thoughts Toward Foreign Language of High School Students In Terms of Private High School/ State High School

Subdimensions	State Private	N	$\bar{X}$	S	Sd	Effect Size	t	P
Overgeneralisation	State	677	2,30	0,91	898	0,12	0,580	0,113
	Private	223	2,19	0,89				
Change effort	State	677	2,62	0,98	898	0,10	1,290	0,195
	Private	223	2,72	0,99				
If only	State	677	3,33	1,07	898	0,31	4,000	0,000*
	Private	223	3,00	1,01				
Polarization	State	677	2,72	1,12	898	0,01	0,213	0,831
	Private	223	2,74	0,96				
Generalisation	State	677	3,02	1,03	898	0,06	1,00	0,317
	Private	223	2,95	0,99				
Definitely	State	677	3,07	0,91	898	0,30	3,97	0,000*
	Private	223	2,80	0,85				
Individualisation	State	677	2,17	0,91	898	0,01	0,220	0,826
	Private	223	2,18	0,88				
Over self-sacrificing	State	677	1,95	0,90	898	0,25	3,12	0,002*
	Private	223	2,17	0,84				

*p<.05

Table 1 revealed that there was a significant difference in "if only", "Definitely", "Over self-sacrificing" subdimensions $t(898) = p < .05$. Students in private school have more stereotyped thoughts than students in state school as to over self-sacrificing subdimension. On the other hand, Students in state school have more stereotyped thoughts than students in private school as to "If only", "Definitely" subdimensions.

2b) "Is there a significant difference between the stereotyped thoughts about foreign language of high school students as to weekly studying hours?"

Table 2: Kruskal Wallis Results of Differences in Stereotyped Thoughts toward Foreign Language of High School Students in Terms of weekly studying hours

Weekly Studying Hours	Mean Rank	Chi Square	df	P
No working	459,88	4,704	5	,453
1-2 hours	451,34			
3-4 hours	456,22			
4-5 hours	468,00			
5-6 hours	399,88			
Over 6 hours	391,81			

*p> .05

Table 2 revealed that there was no significant difference on the stereotyped thoughts toward foreign language as to weekly studying hours $p < .05$.

2c) "Is there a significant difference between the stereotyped thoughts about foreign language of high school students as to English Learning Aims?"

Table 3: Kruskal Wallis Results of Differences in Stereotyped Thoughts Toward Foreign Language of High School Students In Terms of English Learning Aims

English Learning Aims	Mean Rank	Chi Square	df	P
Passing the exams	441,67	16,437	6	,012*
Communicating with the foreigners	451,19			
Finding a good job	497,86			
Going abroad	441,17			
Building a career	437,83			
Indecisive	485,06			
The other	340,48			

* $p > .05$

Table 3 revealed that there was a significant difference on the stereotyped thoughts toward foreign language as to English Learning Aims in high school. The results of Mann Whitney U test was given in Table 4 to find the source of difference.

Table 4: Mann Whitney U Results of Stereotyped Thoughts toward Foreign Language of High School Students In Terms of English Learning Aims

Groups	English Learning Aims	Mean Rank	Z Value	p	Meaningful Difference
Passing the exams	communicating with the foreigners	194,99	-,350	,723	1 < 3
	finding a good job	211,22	-1,967	,049*	1 > 7
	going abroad	176,78	-,102	,919	
	building a career	173,99	-,195	,845	
	indecisive	166,69	-1,242	,214	
	the other	119,31	-2,304	,021*	
Communicating with the foreigners	passing the exams	190,92	-,350	,726	2 > 7
	finding a good job	162,54	-1,638	,101	
	going abroad	130,97	-,380	,704	
	building a career	130,58	-,359	,716	
	indecisive	118,13	-,922	,356	
	the other	81,33	-2,741	,006*	
Finding a good job	passing the exams	188,22	-1,967	,049*	3 > 1
	communicating with the foreigners	145,92	-1,638	,101	3 > 7
	going abroad	127,67	-1,840	,066	
	building a career	126,49	-1,957	,050	
	indecisive	115,53	-,305	,760	
	the other	76,91	3,862	,000*	
Going abroad	passing the exams communicating with the foreigners	176,78	-,102	,919	4 > 7
	finding a good job	134,58	-,380	,704	
	building a career	145,53	-1,840	,066	
		115,75	-,057	,954	

	indecisive	101,49	-1,104	,269	
	the other	71,40	2,233	,026*	
Building a career	passing the exams	176,24	-,195	,845	5>7
	communicating with the foreigners	133,98	,359	,719	
	finding a good job	145,47	-1,957	,050	
	going abroad	116,25	-,057	,954	
	indecisive	101,66	-1,247	,212	
	the other	69,87	-2,433	,015*	
Indecisive	passing the exams	151,93	-1,242	,214	6>7
	communicating with the foreigners	109,67	-,922	,356	
	finding a good job	118,67	-,305	,760	
	going abroad	92,45	-1,104	,269	
	building a career	91,48	-1,247	,212	
	the other	51,65	-3,005	,003*	
The other	passing the exams	148,75	-2,304	,021*	7<1
	communicating with the foreigners	107,06	-2,741	,006*	7<2
	finding a good job	114,67	-3,862	,000*	7<3
	going abroad	89,54	-2,233	,026*	7<4
	building a career	89,54	-2,433	,015*	7<5
	indecisive	71,56	-3,005	,003*	7<6

1: passing the exams 2: communicating with the foreigners 3: finding a good job 4: going abroad 5: building a career 6: indecisive 7: the other

Table 4 revealed that there was a significant difference between communicating with the foreigners, going abroad and passing the exams, that difference stemmed from communicating with the foreigners. There was a significant difference between communicating with foreigners and the other, which difference stemmed from communicating with foreigners. There was a significant difference between passing the exams, the other, communicating with the foreigners and finding a good job, which difference stemmed from communicating with the foreigners. Also, there was a meaningful difference between going abroad and the other, that difference stemmed from going abroad. There was a meaningful difference between building a career and the other, that difference stemmed from building a career. There was a meaningful difference between indecisive and the other, that difference stemmed from indecisive. There was a meaningful difference between the other and all the aims, which difference stemmed from passing the exam.

2a) "Is there a significant difference between English self-efficacy perception of high school students as to private high school/ state high school?"

Table 5: t-Tests Results of English Self-efficacy Perception High School Students In Terms of Private High School/ State High School

Subdimensions	State / Private	N	$\bar{X}$	S	Sd	Effect size	t	P
Reading	State	677	3,04	0,93	898	0,00	0,081	0,935
	Private	223	3,04	1,08				
Writing	State	677	2,80	0,87	898	0,12	1,553	0,121

	Private	223	2,91	0,91				
Listening	State	677	2,96	0,94	898	0,02	0,211	0,833
	Private	223	2,98	1,03				
Speaking	State	677	2,80	0,97	898	0,19	2,616	0,009*
	Private	223	3,00	1,09				

*p> .05

Table 5 revealed that there was a significant difference in “speaking” subdimension $t(898) = p < .05$. Namely, Students in private high school have more speaking self-efficacy perception than students in state high school.

2b) “Is there a significant difference between English self-efficacy perception of high school students as to weekly studying hours?”

Table 6: One Way Analysis of Variances (ANOVA) Results of English Self-efficacy Perception of High School students in Terms of The Weekly Studying Hours

Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P
Between Groups	54,400	5	10,880	15,256	,000*
Within Groups	637,557	894	,713		
Total	691,957	899			

*p < .05

Table 6 revealed that there was a significant difference on English self-efficacy perception of high school students as to weekly studying hours $F = 15, 256, p < .05$. Tamhane analysis was done to find out the source of difference in table 7.

Table 7: Tamhane Analysis Results of English Self-efficacy Perception of High School students In Terms of Weekly studying Hours

Groups	Weekly Working Hours	Mean Rank	df	p	Meaningful Difference
No working	1-2 hours	-,14966	,06121	,200	1<3 1<4 1<6
	3-4 hours	-,35289	,10254	,012*	
	4-5 hours	-,60493	,17645	,030*	
	5-6 hours	-,53557	,17698	,069	
	More than 6 hours	,92216	,13866	,000*	
1-2 hours	No working	,14966	,06121	,200	2<6
	3-4 hours	-,20323	,10000	,495	
	4-5 hours	-,45528	,17499	,205	
	5-6 hours	,38591	,17552	,416	
	More than 6 hours	,77250	,13679	,000*	
3-4 hours	No working	,35289	,10254	,012*	3>1
	1-2 hours	,20323	,10000	,495	
	4-5 hours	-,25204	,19336	,965	
	5-6 hours	,18268	,19385	1,000	
	More than 6 hours	-,56927	,15962	,906	
4-5 hours	No working	,60493	,17645	,069	
	1-2 hours	,45528	,17499	,416	

	3-4 hours	,25204	,19336	,998	
	5-6 hours	,06936	,24124	1,000	
	More than 6 hours	-,38659	,21515	,701	
5-6 hours	No working	,53557	,17698	,069	
	1-2 hours	,38591	,17552	,416	
	3-4 hours	,18268	,19385	,998	
	4-5 hours	-,06936	,24124	1,000	
	More than 6 hours	-,38659	,21515	,701	
More than 6 hours	No working	,92216	,13866	,000*	6>1
	1-2 hours	,77250	,13679	,000*	6>2
	3-4 hours	,58927	,15962	008*	6>3
	4-5 hours	,31723	,21471	,906	
	5-6 hours	,38659	,21515	,701	

1: no working, 2: 1-2 hours, 3: 3-4 hours, 4: 4-5 hours, 5: 5-6 hours 6: more than 6 hours

Table 7 revealed that there was a significant difference between 3-4 hours, 4-5 hours, more than 6 hours and no working, that difference stemmed from 3-4 hours, 4-5 hours, more than 6 hours. There was a significant difference between 1-2 hours and more than 6 hours, that difference stemmed from more than 6 hours. There was a significant difference between 3-4 hours and no working, that difference stemmed from 3-4 hours. There was a significant difference between no working, 1-2 hours 2-3 hours and more than 6 hours, that difference stemmed from more than 6 hours.

2c) "Is there a significant difference between English self-efficacy perception of high school students as to English Learning Aims?"

Table 8: One Way Analysis of Variances (ANOVA) Results of English Self-efficacy Perception of High School students in Terms of English Learning Aims

Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P
Between Groups	125,669	6	20,945	33,029	,000*
Within Groups	566,288	893	,634		
Total	691,957	899			

*p < .05

Table 8 revealed that there was a significant difference on English self-efficacy perception of high school students as to learning aims $F= 33, 029$ $p < .05$. LSD analysis was done to find out the source of difference in table 21.

Table 9: LSD Analysis Results of English Self-efficacy Perception of High School students In Terms of English Learning Aims

Groups	English Learning Aims	Mean Rank	df	p	Meaningful Difference
Passing the exams	communicating with the foreigners	,68313	,08339	,000*	1<2
	finding a good job	-,47824	,08177	,000*	1<3
	going abroad	-1,04520	,09036	,000*	1<4
		-,83148	,09062	,000*	1<5

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	building a career	-,30841	,10561	,004*	1<6
	indecisive	-,99219	,12301	,000*	1<7
	the other				
Communicating with the foreigners	passing the exams	,68313	,08339	,000*	2>1
	finding a good job	,20488	,09080	,024*	2>3
	going abroad	-,36207	,09860	,000*	2<4
	building a career	-,14835	,09884	,134	2>6
	indecisive	,37472-	,11274	,001*	2<7
	the other	,30907	,12919	,017*	
Finding a good job	passing the exams	,47824	,08177	,000*	3>1
	communicating with the foreigners	-,20488	,09080	,024*	3<2
	going abroad	-,56695	,09724	,000*	3<4
	building a career	-,35324	,10479	,000*	3<5
	indecisive	,16983	,11799	,128	3<7
	the other	-,51395	,13379	,000*	
Going abroad	passing the exams	1,04520	,09036	,000*	4>1
	communicating with the foreigners	,36207	,09860	,000*	4>2
	finding a good job	,56695	,09724	,000*	4>3
	building a career	,21372	,10479	,042*	4>5
	indecisive	,73678	,11799	,000*	4>6
	the other	,05300	,13379	,692	4>7
Building a career	passing the exams	,83148	,09062	,000*	5>1
	communicating with the foreigners	,14835	,09884	,134	5>3
	finding a good job	,35324	,09748	,000*	5<4
	going abroad	-,21372	,10479	,042*	5>6
	indecisive	,52307	,11819	,000*	5<7
	the other	-,16071	,13397	,231	
Indecisive	passing the exams	,30841	,10561	,004*	6>1
	communicating with the foreigners	-,37472	,11274	,001*	6<2
	finding a good job	-,16983	,11155	,128	6<4
	going abroad	,73678	,11799	,000*	6<5
	building a career	-,52307	,11819	,000*	6<7
	the other	-,68378	,14453	,000*	
The other	passing the exams	,99219	,12301	,000*	7>1
	communicating with the foreigners	,30907	,12919	,017*	7>2
	finding a good job	,51395	,12815	,000*	7>3
	going abroad	-,05300	,13379	,692	7>6
	building a career indecisive	16071	,13397	,231	
		,68378	,14453	,000*	

1: passing the exams 2: communicating with the foreigners 3: finding a good job 4: going abroad 5: building a career 6: indecisive 7: the other

Table 9 revealed that there was a significant difference between communicating with the foreigners, finding a good job, going abroad, building a career, indecisive, the other and passing the exams, that difference stemmed from the other. There was a significant

difference between finding a good job, passing the exams, communicating with the foreigners, the other and going abroad, that difference stemmed from going abroad.

3) Is there a correlation between the stereotyped thoughts about foreign language and English self-efficacy perception of high school students?

Table 10: Pearson's-r Correlation Result for The Significant Relationship between Stereotyped Thoughts about Foreign Language and English Self-efficacy Perception of high School Students

		Stereotyped Thoughts About Foreign Language	English Self-efficacy Perception
Stereotyped Thoughts About Foreign Language	Correlation	1,00	-, 013
	P		,691
	N	900	900
English Self-efficacy Perception	Correlation	-, 013	1,00
	P	,691	
	N	900	900

*p<,01

Table 10 revealed that there was no significant relationship between stereotyped thoughts about foreign language and English Self-efficacy perception ($r = ,691$; $p > ,01$).

4) "Can stereotyped thoughts about foreign language of high school students predict English self-efficacy perception of students?"

Table 11: Regression Analysis Results

Dependent variable	Predictor Variable	R	R ²	F	B	β	Sig
Stereotyped Thoughts	English Self-efficacy	,013	,000	,158	-,018	-,013	,691

*p<,05

The results of the regression analysis show that stereotyped thoughts can not predict English self-efficacy. The p value is not statistically meaningful for stereotyped thoughts and English self-efficacy. ($p = ,691$ $p > ,05$)

4. Conclusion and Discussion

There was no significant difference in "over generalisation", "change effort", "polarization", "individualisation" and "generalization" subdimensions in terms of private/ state school in their stereotyped thoughts of high school students. But There was a significant difference in "if only", "definitely" and "over self-sacrificing" sub-dimension. Houghton (2010) concluded that students must assess the advantages and disadvantages of stereotyped thoughts and the needs to overcome potential difficulties and that experiential learning is a good way to control cognitive awareness and

stereotyped thoughts. It is important to increase experiential learning to reduce stereotyped thoughts towards language learning at schools.

There was no significant difference on the stereotyped thoughts toward foreign language as to weekly studying hours.

There was a significant difference on the stereotyped thoughts toward foreign language as to English Learning aims in high school. That difference stemmed from passing the exams, finding a good job and communicating with foreigners.

There was a significant difference in “speaking” subdimension on English self-efficacy perception of students as to private/state high school. Namely, Students in private high school have more speaking self-efficacy perception than students in state high school. Seraoui (2016) concluded that comfortable environments for learning make speaking skills improve by increasing self-efficacy perception. It can be said that private schools are equipped with teaching environments and the number of weekly lessons per week is higher than that of the official schools, which leads to increase in speech self- efficacy perceptions of these students. Liu (2013) stated that communicating with the foreigners increases speaking self-efficacy. Native speakers in private schools may cause speaking self-efficacy of students to increase. There was a significant difference on English self-efficacy perception of high school students as to types of high school. That difference stemmed from science high school and social sciences. On the contrary, that work, Memduhoğlu ve Çelik (2015) found no significant difference on self-efficacy perception of students in Anatolian high school and general high school. Berberoğlu and Kalender (2005) stated that science and Anatolian high schools are more successful than the other high school students and they had higher self-efficacy perceptions. In this research, having high self-efficacy perception in science high school showed similarity with this study. Schunk ve Meece (2009) concluded that the students studying in the school that are more academically successful students feel inadequate and this leads to decrease in self-efficacy perception.

There was a significant difference on English self-efficacy perception of high school students as to weekly studying hours. That difference stemmed from 3-4 hours and over than 6 hours. According to that study, Students having higher working hours have more self-efficacy perception. On the contrary, that findings of that study, Hewitt (2008) concluded that the duration on teaching foreign language does not affect academic self-efficacy and language achievement.

There was a significant difference on English self-efficacy perception of high school students as to learning aims. That difference stemmed from going abroad, the other and building career. Gagunhu (2007) studied on strategies on French language learning and self-efficacy. Gagunhu investigated the reason of leaning French and % 25 of participants gave specific answers. % 58 of participants gave unclear answers and %17 of them stated that they had no aim to learn French.

It was investigated whether there was a correlation between stereotyped thoughts about foreign language and English self-efficacy perception or not. According to the result of study, there was no correlation between stereotyped thoughts about

foreign language and English self-efficacy perception. Yanar (2008) found that there was a positive and meaningful correlation between English self-efficacy and attitudes toward English. Ocak ve Akkaş (2016) found that there was a positive and meaningful correlation between language learning strategies and English self-efficacy. Gahungu (2007) found that there was a positive and high correlation between using strategies and self-efficacy. Açıkkel (2011) found that there was a negative and meaningful correlation between using repetition and memory strategies and English self-efficacy.

As a final problem, regression analysis showed that stereotyped thoughts can not predict English self-efficacy. Hackett and Betz (1989) found that regression analysis supported the superiority of mathematics self-efficacy over mathematics performance and achievement variables in predicting the choice of a mathematics-related major. Pajares (2006) found that science self-efficacy predicts science achievement. Paul and Gore (2006) found that academic self-efficacy beliefs predict college outcomes.

Based on the findings of this analysis we can try to increase self-efficacy perception of the students and to lessen the stereotyped thoughts of students so as to improve their language learning. As a suggestion, more research is needed to find out the effects of different variables on self-efficacy perception and stereotyped thoughts.

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